

DILATOMETRIC STUDIES ON SUPERSATURATION. PART I.

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It has been confirmed that no sudden change in volume occurs at the saturation temperature when a solution is cooled from unsaturated to the supersaturated state in the cases of solutions of potassium nitrate, sodium nitrate, potassium sulphate, sodium acetate and oxalic acid in water. It has been demonstrated that inflexions in temperature-volume curves of any cooling solution occur only when crystallisation takes place, either automatically, or is induced artificially by inoculation. An attempt has also been made to show that no sudden changes which can be exhibited as changes in volume of a cooling solution occur in the molecular state at the lower limit of the metastable range *i.e.*, at the labile temperature.

It has been shown by various workers that the physical properties *e.g.*, conductivity (Heim, *Ann. Physik*, 1886, *iii*, 27, 673), specific viscosity (Nichol, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, *81*, 389; Taimini, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, *2*, 604), specific gravity, specific heat, heat of solution (Bindel, *Ann. Phys. Chem.*, 1890, *iii*, 40, 370) and density (Scott and Badger, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1936, *40*, 461) of supersaturated solutions do not suffer any abrupt change either at the saturation temperature or at any other point below this temperature to which it has been possible to cool the solution before spontaneous crystallisation sets in.

The works of Miers and Issac (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, *89*, 413) appear to show, however, that a change in solution occurs at the metastable temperature. The experiments carried out by Nayar (*Proc. Acad. Sci., U.P.*, 1931, *1*, 100) on dilatation of supersaturated solutions seem to corroborate the conclusions of Miers and Issac and further claim to establish a break at the saturation point. But experiments of Hook (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, *41*, 593) point out that temperature-volume curves of a number of solutions "show no non-uniformity at the saturation point." As experiments of Hook are in general agreement with the hypothesis that the physical properties do not suffer any discontinuity at the saturation temperature, the experimental results obtained in the preliminary investigations of Nayar pointing out such a break require further investigation.

Oxalic Acid Solution.

Aqueous solutions of different substances, saturated at temperatures varying from 50° to 70°, were put successively into a dilatometer similar to that of Nayar (*loc. cit.*) after filtering so as to remove dust particles,

that might be present in the salts. Solutions were immediately covered with a layer of paraffin oil in order to prevent any evaporation which might alter the saturation temperature of the solution. The bulb of the dilatometer was dipped in a big beaker containing water. Further the beaker was covered with cotton pads, with a little opening left for taking observations. This device was adopted to ensure a slow cooling. The solution was then heated to a temperature approximately 10° higher than the saturation point and the apparatus was completely fitted up as was done by Nayar and Hook. Then the beaker was allowed to cool slowly. Changes in volume were read on the capillary tube fitted on a metre scale. The rate of cooling was controlled by a micro-burner put under the beaker.

In the table given below, scale readings are recorded along with the corresponding time and temperature for the oxalic acid solution.

TABLE I.

Oxalic acid solution.

Time.	Temp.	Scale readings.	Time.	Temp.	Scale readings.
0 min.	76°	99'0	76 min.	58° C.T.*	26'0
—	74	92'2	80	$58^{\circ}4$	18'0
14	72	85'3	—	$58^{\circ}5$	15'0
22	70	77'5	—	$58^{\circ}8$	10'0
30	68 S.T.*	69'2	—	$59^{\circ}0$	6'0
40	66	60'3	—	$58^{\circ}5$	4'0
49	64	51'6	86	$58^{\circ}3$	3'0
59	62	43'0	90	$58^{\circ}0$	0'0
65	60	34'0	97	$57^{\circ}3$	-3'0

From the above table the temperature-volume curve for oxalic acid was drawn as shown in Fig. 1, curve A. In all other cases similar readings were obtained and graphs B, C, D and E were drawn and are given in Fig. 1.

From the curves given in Fig. 1 it is apparent that the graphs can be divided into two different types. The first type contains an inflexion while the second type is without it. In all these cases, however, one thing

* S.T. denotes the saturation temperature and C.T. the temperature at which crystallisation is observed to start

is common *i.e.*, no discontinuity occurs at the point where the solutions pass from the unsaturated into the supersaturated or metastable state. In every case in which spontaneous crystallisation occurs (curves A, B, C and D) there is a change in the direction of the curve at the point where crystalli-

Fig. 1.

sation begins with a consequent release of supersaturation at a little lower temperature. The magnitude and shape of the inflexion depend upon the quantity of heat evolved and the amount of the crystals formed on the release of supersaturation. In the second type (curve E) *i.e.*, in the case of sodium acetate, which is capable of remaining in the supersaturated condition to a great extent, no crystallisation took place even when -8° was reached, the saturation temperature being 58° . It is clear therefore that sodium acetate does not crystallise within the limits of the temperatures tried and no break in the curve is noticed.

From the curves it can also be seen that inflexion is well marked in the case of oxalic acid, not so clear in the case of potassium sulphate and does not occur at all in the case of sodium acetate. This is due to

the fact that comparatively large amount of crystals is released in the case of oxalic acid, temperature coefficient of solubility being 2.7 g. per degree, whereas in the case of potassium sulphate, etc., quantity released is small, the temperature coefficient of solubility being 0.2 g. per degree.

It is therefore clear that the inflexion in temperature-volume curve at the saturation temperature observed by Nayar is merely due to crystallisation that sets in at that point and that it is not a characteristic of the saturation temperature itself. This is to say there occurs no sudden change in the volume of a solution as it passes from the unsaturated into the supersaturated state indicating no sudden change in the state of the entities concerned at the saturation temperature. Continuing the same trend of reasoning, there is no reason to suppose that a sudden change in the volume should occur at the lower limit of the metastable range (*i.e.*, at the labile temperature) unless of course crystallisation sets in. For example, in the case of sodium chlorate solution crystallisation does not occur even at the labile temperature (Miers, *loc. cit.*). Even moderate shaking has no effect and the solution passes far into the labile region without crystallising. A similar case is noticed in sodium acetate solution although no supersolubility data is available in the literature. If, therefore, we bring about crystallisation in these cases by inoculation, curves similar to that of oxalic acid should be obtained. Conversely, if crystallisation in oxalic acid be stopped somehow, the inflexions observed should disappear or at least shifted to some lower temperature where crystallisation may set in. With a view to get further information on this point experiments given below were carried out.

Oxalic Acid Solution with Inoculation.

Oxalic acid solutions to which varying amounts of gelatine were added crystallised at the same temperature as pure oxalic acid solution indicating no effect of added gelatine.

The next procedure suggested above, *i.e.* to induce crystallisation by inoculation in sodium acetate and sodium chlorate solutions was therefore adopted. Sodium chlorate solution, however, began to crystallise at the saturation temperature in presence of oil. But sodium acetate solution gave very satisfactory results, hence it was utilised in the following set of experiments.

The simple dilatation apparatus used in the previous experiments is modified so as to enable one to inoculate the cooling solution with a minute crystal of the substance without disturbing the rest of the apparatus, at

any desired temperature. It carries an upright side-tube of approximately the same height as the neck of the dilatometer. At the upper end of the tube an arrangement is made to enable one to drop a germ crystal into the solution by slightly twisting the handle of the crystal-carrying cup as is the case in the vapour density apparatus of Victor Meyer. The whole arrangement is made air-tight. The temperature readings are taken as before and the graphs given in Figs. 2 and 3 below are obtained from them.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

In order to investigate a wide range of temperatures with the same capillary tubing the following device is adopted in the cases represented by the curves E of Fig. 1 and by those of Fig. 2. "No readings are taken until the solution cools down to the temperature marked by the letter N on the curves of these figures. At this temperature recording is started. The scale reading at this temperature is brought to 100 cm. approximately in every case. This is done by attaching a bent capillary tubing filled with oil to the main capillary tube and dipping the end of the bent tube in a beaker containing oil. It is disconnected when the solution cools down to the required temperature." In Fig. 3 the initial reading for every curve is 100 cm. and 72°. Inoculation in Fig. 2 are made at 52°, 31° and 16°; while in Fig. 3 at 52°, 42°, and 35°. The straight portions of the curves in Fig. 3 are almost coincident except a little deviation due to the experimental errors.

From these series of graphs it is clear that a crystallisation process is always accompanied by an inflexion in the curve. But the curves E in Fig. 1 show that if there is no crystallisation there is no inflexion. The graphs of Figs. 2 and 3 are of the type of oxalic acid. Hence these experiments conclusively prove that inflexions can be produced at any desired temperature within the supersaturated region by bringing about crystallisation at that temperature artificially by inoculation. If we suppose that the labile temperature for sodium acetate solution studied here is included within this wide region of supersaturation (from 58° to -8°), and this seems to be fairly certain as the solution sets to solid mass immediately on inoculation, it can be said with a fair degree of accuracy that no inflexion occurs even at the lower limit of the metastable range, *i.e.*, at the labile temperature of Mjers.

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